

www.arseam.com

“IMPACT OF EMPLOYEES’ TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMMES ON BHEL” - An Evaluation

Dr. N.P. Maheshwari

* Reader, Dept. of
Commerce, Govt P.G.
College, Rishikesh

** Research Scholar, Dept.
of Commerce, Govt. P.G.
College, Rishikesh.

Dr. Ashok Kumar *

Reader, Dept. of Commerce,
Govt P.G. College, Rishikesh
** Research Scholar, Dept. of
Commerce, Govt. P.G.
College, Rishikesh.

Parul Garg ***

Reader, Dept. of
Commerce, Govt P.G.
College, Rishikesh
** Research Scholar,
Dept. of Commerce, Govt.
P.G. College, Rishikesh.

Abstract

Training and development maybe defined as any organizationally planned effort to change the behaviour or attitudes of employees so that they can perform jobs on acceptable standards. Training provides knowledge and skills required to perform the job. Development is viewed similarly but with more stress on communicating organizational norms and values for the given roles and thus becomes, in part, a socialization process.

Key words: BHEL, employee, Training and development.

Introduction

In the current scenario, business environment is changing rapidly and rules of game is the survival of the fittest whether in public or private sector . In these circumstances, training and development of employees is a continuous process of any organization. The role of training and development is more important in public sector because of the likely changes in the government policies during the reform process. Thus, the training has assumed a great importance in an economy since it has become not only important but also imperative to compete in the global economy. In the current global scenario the only competitive advantage which differentiate the successful factors of various organizations is effective knowledge enhancement. Training and development is all about enriching human resource.

BHEL - AN OVERVIEW

The first plant of what is now known as BHEL, was established more than 50 years ago at Bhopal (in 1956) and was the genesis of the heavy electrical equipment industry in India. **BHEL is today, the largest engineering and manufacturing enterprise of its kind in India, with a well recognized track record of performance, earning continuously since 1971-72.** It achieved a sales turnover of Rs 10336 crore with a net profit of Rs 953 crore in 2004-2005.

The company today enjoys national and international presence featuring in the “fortune International 500” and is ranked among the top ten companies in the world for manufacturing power generation equipments. The companies inherent potential coupled with its strong performance over the years, has resulted in its being chosen as one of the ‘NAVRATNA’ PSEs.

HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT IN BHEL

The most prized asset of BHEL are its 43302 employees, out of which 41359 (95%) employees were exposed to different training and development programmes in HRDI at Noida and HRDCs at units during the year 2004-05. The Human Resource Development Institute (HRDI) and other HRD centers of the company help in not only keeping their skills updated and finely honed but also add new skills when required. The continues training, retaining, managerial development, a positive work culture and participative style of management have led

to the development of a committed and motivated work force, enhanced productivity and quality levels in the organization.

Exhibit-1
HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT IN BHEL

Sr.No	Year	Nos. of Employees	Nos Trained	Percentage Trained
1	2000-01	52225	42573	82%
2	2001-02	47516	40172	84%
3	2002-03	46855	40000	85%
4	2003-04	43952	30000	68%
5	2004-05	43302	41359	95%

SOURCE: Compiled by Annual Reports 2000-01 to 2004-05

The following figures compiled in exhibit-1 are evident of rapid growth of human resource development in BHEL through its HRD Centres at units and HRDI at NOIDA. Exhibit-1 shows that trained employees in BHEL are more than 80% except the year 2003-4 while HRDI has a major role to play, much of human resource development in BHEL is also done through its several HRD centres located at the divisions/units. The HRDC and HRDI network together is as follows:

HRD Centre-BHEL Hardwar

The HRD centre was established in the year 1963. From technical training school to Training school and also from training school to human resources development centre, the journey has kept in focus the advancement of performing trade skills and managerial potential of vast human resource composing of executives, supervisors and workers. Over a period of 40 long years the centre itself has bagged the Best Establishment award more than 20 times which is a record in itself for any training centre in the country. Developmental training started in the year 1975. Since then the HRD Centre has not looked back. In a span of more than 30 year the Centre has trained about one lakh twenty thousand employees at various levels, the yearly average being 4000nos./year. The development programmes covered both in-house and external programmes including corporate HRDI programme.

Human Resource Development Institute

The idea of setting up the Human Resource Development Institute was conceived in BHEL's first corporate plan in 1974. The institute came in to existence in 1976 to fulfill one of the corporate objectives viz.; "to ensure continuous development of competent managerial personnel and make the best use of both the human and material resources." All through the 30 years of its existence, the institute has played a significant role in ensuring continuous development of managerial personnel. This is amply evident from nearly 660 programmes conducted so far concerning about 14000 participants.

THRUST AREAS FOR TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT IN BHEL

The following on going training programmes in the BHEL reflects the thrust areas of training and development imparted through the various HRD centers and HRDI at Noida.

1. General Management programmes (GMP)

2. **Advanced Management Programmes (AMP)**
3. **Young Managers Programmes (YMP)**
4. **Strategic Management Programmes (SMP)**
5. **Functional Management Programmes (FMP)**
 - i) Project Management
 - ii) Marketing Strategies in the Globalized Economy
 - iii) Formulation of contracts for projects, contract management and financing of projects
 - iv) Formulation, execution and interpretation of contractual terms and conditions for business deals in new globalized economy
 - v) Negotiation Skills
 - vi) IT & E-commerce
6. **Behavioral Programmes**
7. **Special Programmes:**

EVALUATION OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT PROG_S IN BHEL

Apart from the financial performance of the BHEL, impact of training and development programmes have also been evaluated on the basis of various indicators such as-Machine tools utilization percentage, Savings due to production improvement plan, impact on grievances, training mandays per employee, inventory level, award and recognitions etc.

Therefore, to evaluate the impact of training and development programmes in BHEL, the study have been divided into two parts as follows:

A- Impact on financial performance and market price data of BHEL

B- Other indicators

A- IMPACT ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE AND MARKET PRICE DATA OF BHEL

i. Training mean financial Performance:

Human Capital investments rarely appear on corporate balance sheets, except as an expenditure and not an investments. Consequently it's not surprising that there is little information on the effectiveness of such investments, even within companies. The absence of such information makes it difficult for corporate decision-makers to make well-informed choices about how much money to spend on training or what types of training to offer.

The American Society for Training and development now has preliminary evidence that companies that invest more heavily in training are more successful and profitable. Such companies are also more highly valued on well street, and their market value is growing .

The following figures compiled in Exhibit-2 represents the growing relationship between training and financial performance of BHEL.

Exhibit-2
Financial Performance Highlights: Year 2004-2005

S.No.	Particulars	UNIT	2003-04	2004-05	Up by %
1	Sales Turnover	Rs. Crore	8662	10336.00	19.32 %
2	Value Addition	Rs. Crore	3680	4254	15.60 %
3	Gross Profit(PBT)	Rs. Crore	1015	1582	55.85 %
4	Net Profit	Rs. Crore	658	953	44.85 %
5	Dividend Per Share	Rs.	6	8	33.33 %
6	EPS	Rs.	26.89	38.95	44.86 %
7	NAV Per Share	Rs.	215.64	246.24	14.19 %
8	Value Added Per Emp.	Rs. Lakh	8.37	9.82	17.32 %
9	Turnover Per Emp	Rs. Lakh	19.70	23.86	21.17 %
10	Emoluments Per Emp.	Rs. Lakh	3.73	3.81	2.18 %
11	Gross Profit Per Emp.	Rs. Lakh	2.30	3.65	58.84 %

From the above Exhibit-2 we can understand that financial performance of BHEL is very sound. Sales turnover, value addition, gross profit, net profit etc., are increasing on the one hand and dividend per share, EPS, NAV per share, value added per employee, gross profit per employee have an increasing trend on the other. Turnover per employee is 21 percent up in the corresponding year 2004-2005. Thus we can conclude that beside other reasons, continuous on going training and development programmes are one of the very important factors in reaping financial rewards in BHEL.

ii. Performance and Market Price Data

One powerful source to measure companies performance is the stock market. A stock price is assumed to reflect investors' beliefs about long-term firm performance. Thus fluctuations in stock price, or other measures derived from equity indicators, can be taken as index of the firm's future performance potential. If this assumption is accepted, then some strategic initiative i.e. the training and development, should impact the firm's stock market performance. If the move is anticipated to improve performance in the long term. The exhibit reveals that during 2004-05, BHEL recorded Net Worth Rs. 246.2 per share up by 14.19%, Earning Per Share Rs. 38.95, up by about 44.86% and dividend Rs. 8.00 per share up 33.3, compared to Rs. 215.6, Rs 26.89 and Rs 6.00 respectively of the last fiscal 2003-2004. **Apart from this, Share Market Price high and low quotations of Shares traded on the stock Exchange Mumbai during the year 2004-05 indicates an upward trend in equity prices of BHEL shown as under in Exhibit-3:**

Exhibit-3
Showing Market Share prices of BHEL in BSE, MUMBAI

S.No	Month & Year	Bombay Stock Exchange Prices	
		High	Low
1.	April 2004	686.00	580.25
2.	March 2005	883.00	741.60

SOURCE : www.bseindia.com

Presently, market share price of BHEL at BSE, Mumbai is quoting sound Rs. 1800 per share.

B. Other important indicators showing the employees effectiveness in BHEL due to T& D Programmes

- As a result of training & development to employees inventory level in amount and in number of days to turnover have come down to 153 days in 2004-05 from 235 inventory days during the year 2000-2001.
- With the improvement in benefits and training & development programmes, employees are motivated. This led to continuous reduction in absenteeism
- There is an increasing trend in training mandays per employee and amount spent on training and development per employee. The training mandays per employee rose to 4.12 days during the year 2004-05 as compared to 2.2 days in the year 2003-04.
- Due to improvement employees performance material cost reduced upto 254, 275 and 342 Lakhs during 1999-2000, 2000-2001 and 2001-02 respectively.
- Machine tool utilization percentage have been increased.
- Savings due to production improvement plan (PIP) per executive due to suggestions per employee is improving.
- Number of mandays due to LWP and commuted have a decreasing trend thus, enhanced the workers efficiency.
- Number of registered grievances as defined in grievance redressal scheme at unit level is almost NIL since last many years.
- Return on capital employed have an increasing trend. As it was respectively 35, 39 and 76 percent in the consecutive years 2002-2003, 2003-04 and 2004-05.

□ **Awards and Recognitions:**

A large number of employees of BHEL have been honored with the coveted Prime Minister's SHRAMVIR, SHRAM SHRI , SHRAM DEVI and VISHWA KARMA National Awards. For the year 2004-05, 14 workmen of BHEL have got 8 PM's Shram Awards (highest in any year), including the only Shram Bhushan Award declared this year.

BHEL has also won a number of national and international awards which include Best Material Handling Award by National Handling Council, Jamshedpur, Best Organization Award by Indra Gandhi Memorial National Award Committee, INSAAN Award for Excellence in Suggestion Scheme Association and Best Organization Award for Excellence in Value Engineering by Society of Indian Value Management. BHEL has the rare distinction of getting Sword of Honor Award from British safety Council, London.

BHEL also bagged the topmost position amongst PSUs in the Best Employers survey, reflecting the high level of satisfaction of its employees. The survey covering, 204 public and private sector companies, was conducted by Business Today and Hewitt Associates.

CONCLUSION

Now, there is preliminary evidence that BHEL through its training and development is reaping financial rewards. Though much additional work has to be done in this area, there is growing evidence that companies must treat training & development as an investment and measure them accordingly.

Thus, it can be concluded from the above evaluations that a sense of belongingness has been developed in the employees due to various distinct programmes of training and development being carried out in BHEL. This is the only reason due to which there has never been any strike and lock-out in the company. The credit for this goes to very remarkable industrial relations which it has maintained by virtue of training & development programmes. Briefly this is the fundamental reason for the continuous growth and progress of largest plant of its kind, manufacturing Hydro sets in the world today. That's why BHEL duly deserves to be NAVRATNA's of the Indian Government.